

Original Research Article

Assessment of Nurses Knowledge and Practices Regarding to Safe Oxygen Administration Therapy

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Abstract

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Oxygen therapy is one of the main interventions that is used to manage the respiratory abnormalities. Oxygen therapy is a basic requirement prescribed largely for hypoxic patients. It depending on the basic medical condition of a patient, and whether the condition is acute or chronic, the best amount and method of oxygen delivery system. The uses of oxygen to those patients who have adverse events related to respiration, such as unexpected death, cardiac arrest, or accidental intensive care unit admissions. In this study it is important to check the knowledge and practices of nurses about the administration of oxygen on critical patients in ICU and medical and surgical ward and enhance their practices. A descriptive study design will be used in this research study. The study will be conducted in the different ICUs, CCU, Emergencies and medical and surgical wards, in Sheikh Zayed hospital Lahore. The population for this study is the nurses including graduated nurses, diploma holder nurses, nurses who have more than 1 year of experience. 133 is a sample size for this study. Random sampling technique used for this study. The likert scale questionnaire is used for knowledge assessment and observation tool is used to assess the practices of the nurses on a safe oxygen administration therapy. The mean score of knowledge is ± 1.01 , the practices before administration of oxygen mean score is ± 1.08 , during oxygen administration mean score is ± 0.93 , and after oxygen administration means score is ± 1.045 . This study concluded that, a majority of the studied sample had satisfactory level of knowledge and had adequate level of practices.

Keywords: Administration, Knowledge, Nurses, Oxygen, Practices, Therapy

INTRODUCTION

Oxygen therapy is one of the primary interventions that is used to cope the respiratory abnormalities. Nurses plays a dynamic role in the management of oxygen administration in patients at vulnerability of respiratory dysfunction. Oxygen therapy is a basic requirement prescribed largely for hypoxic patients (Eastwood, 2012). Depending on the basic medical condition of a patient, and whether the condition is acute or chronic, the best

amount and method of oxygen delivery system. The selection of the best oxygen delivery system and the oxygen flow rate depends on many factors including the age of patient, the clinical objectives and patient tolerance (Aloushan, 2019). The nurse regularly examines the mucous membranes of the mouth and skin for marks of interruption (Mostafa, 2019). The nurses are thought to be responsible for the clinical signs and

symptoms of oxygen therapy (Al, 2019). Oxygen harmfulness consequences starting hypoglycemia caused by hypoxia in the brain. This decreases the blood glucose concentration by 15–20 percent and therefore the glucose available for transportation through the blood brain wall (Wilson, 2019). Pulmonary oxygen toxicity is an advanced disease indicated by acute tracheobronchitis that shows with respiration as cough and burning sensation. Results may include level of auscultation, atelectasis, non-cardiogenic pulmonary edema, acute lung parenchymal injury, and/or chronic lung injury (Cronin, 2019). Many incidents of acute respiratory failure can be detected by measuring blood hemoglobin oxygen saturation. Obtaining accurate data regarding the oxygenation saturation of hemoglobin in blood (SaO₂) requires invasive arterial blood gas (ABG) analysis. Noninvasive measurement of arterial SpO₂ is obtained by an instrument called a pulse oximeter (Amalakanti, 2016). The initial treatment for a seizure triggered by oxygen is to reduce the inspired Po₂. It is done by reducing the atmospheric pressure, exchanging to a breathing mixture with a lower oxygen level, or both. Diminishing inspired Po₂ cannot reverse the effects of CNS O₂ toxicity immediately and is not without risk (Manning, 2016)

Problem Statement

Repeated and frequently fixed with conservative oxygen therapy delivered through also nasal prongs, with fraction of inspired oxygen and flow directed to the degree of hypoxemia (Young, 2020).

Significance of Study

In this study it is important to check the knowledge and practices of nurses about the administration of oxygen on critical patients in ICU and medical and surgical ward and enhance their practices.

Objective

Determine the knowledge and practices of nurses regarding safe oxygen administration therapy.

Operational Definition

Oxygen administered through two foremost categories, low flow delivery systems or high flow delivery systems. Low flow oxygen systems include nasal cannula and low flow masks. High flow devices are also known as fixed performance masks (McGloin, 2008).

Conceptual Definition

Administration of Oxygen depend on patient condition and it has two main categories low flow through nasal cannula, and oxygen mask and high flow (through fixed mask) oxygen therapy.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

A descriptive study design will be used in this research study.

Study Site

This study will be conducted in the sheikh zayed hospital Lahore.

Settings

The study will be conducted in the Medical ICU, Surgical ICU, Peds ICU, Kidney transplant ICU, Liver transplant ICU, CCU, Emergencies and medical and surgical wards, in Sheikh Zayed hospital Lahore.

Target population

The population for this study is the nurses including graduated nurses, diploma holder nurses, nurses who have more than 1 year of experience. The total population of different (ICUs), CCU, Emergencies and medical and surgical ward nurses are 200 and 133 is a sample size for this study.

Data Collection Plan

The likert scale questionnaire is used for knowledge assessment and observation tool is used to assess the practices of the nurses on a safe oxygen administration therapy.

Equipment

In this study, the tool is adopted from (Browne, 2012). The demographic data consist of age, gender, qualifications, years of experience, department, and working shift. And observational tool knowledge assesses on satisfactory and unsatisfactory, and observational tool is check through done or not done.

Validity and reliability

The validity and reliability of the questions checked with cronbach's Alpha on SPSS version 2.0 which is .500.

Ethical Consideration

- All written informed consent attached will be obtained from all the respondents.
- All data collection and information will be kept private.
- Throughout the study, participant's identity will be private.
- The subjects will be informed that the study procedure does not present any disadvantages or risk.
- They will also be informed that during the study process they will be free to withdraw at any time.
- The data is kept in under the key and locked while the keys are kept in hand. It will be kept under password in laptop.

Data Analysis

Data analyzed on SPSS version 21.0 frequencies, percentage, mean applied on individual item. Data is collected through questionnaire and observational checklist in 133 participants.

RESULTS

Part 1 Demographic Data

Gender

Table 1. Shows that 98.5% (n= 133) are female.

Gender	F	%
Female	133	98.5
Total	133	100.0

Age

Table 2. Shows that 37.8% (n=51) age is 20- < 30 years, 43.7% (n= 59) age is 31- < 40 years, 12.6% (n=17) age is 41- < 50 years, 4.4% (n=6) age is 51- <60 years.

Age	F	%
20- <30 year	51	37.8
31- <40 year	59	43.7
41- <50 year	17	12.6
51- < 60 year	6	4.4
Total	133	100.0

Qualification

Table 3, Shows that 82.2% (n= 111) were diploma nurses, and 16.3 % (n= 22) were bachelor nurses.

Qualification	F	%
Diploma nurse	111	82.2
Bachelor	22	16.3
Total	133	100.0

Experience

Table 4. Shows that 63.7% (n= 86) nurses have 1- < 10 years, 25.2% (n=34) nurses have 11- < 20 years, 5.9% (n=8) nurses have 21- <30 years, 3.7% (n=5) nurses have 31+ experience.

Experience	F	%
1-<10 years	86	63.7
11- <20 years	34	25.2
21- <30 years	8	5.9
31+ years	5	3.7
Total	133	100.0

Department

Table 5. Shows that 7.4% (n= 10) nurses were from medical ward, 5.2% (n=7) nurses were from surgical ward, 85.9% (n=116) nurses were from critical care unit.

Department	F	%
Medical ward	10	7.4
Surgical ward	7	5.2
Critical care unit	116	85.9
Total	133	100.0

Part 2

Section No. 1

This section checked nurses knowledge related to safe oxygen administration therapy.

Table 6 shows that nurses answered their question related to safe oxygen administration therapy. Do you know the aim of administration oxygen therapy? 97.8% (n=132) answered yes, 0.7% (n=1) answered no. do you know the indication of oxygen therapy? 100.0% (n= 133) answered yes, there were no participant who said no. Do you know the method of assessing oxygen saturation in the blood? 100.0% (n= 133) answered yes, there were no participant who said no. Do you aware about the precaution during administering oxygen therapy? 95.6% (n= 129) answered yes, 3.0% (n= 4) answered no. Have you know about the oxygen toxicity? 94.8% (n= 128) answered yes, 3.7% (n= 5) answered no. Have you know about the sign and symptoms of oxygen toxicity? 97.0%

(n=131) answered yes, 1.5% (n= 2) answered no. Do you know the complication of oxygen toxicity? 96.3% (n= 130) answered yes, 2.2% (n= 3) answered no. Do you know the medical treatment of oxygen toxicity? 97.8% (n= 132) answered yes, 0.7% (n=1) answered no. Do you know the nursing intervention in case of oxygen toxicity occurrence? 98.5% (n= 133) answered yes, there were no participant who said no. The overall mean of all questions are 1.01.

Table 6. Knowledge related to safe oxygen administration therapy

Sr.no	Statements	Yes		No		Mean
		F	%	F	%	
1.	Do you know the aim of administration oxygen therapy?	132	97.8	1	0.7	1.01
2.	Do you know the indication of oxygen therapy?	133	100.0	0	0	1.00
3.	Do you know the method of assessing oxygen saturation in the blood?	133	100.0	0	0	1.00
4.	Do you aware about the precaution during administering oxygen therapy?	129	95.6	4	3.0	1.03
5.	Have you know about the oxygen toxicity?	128	94.8	5	3.7	1.04
6.	Have you know about the signs and symptoms of oxygen toxicity?	131	97.0	2	1.5	1.02
7.	Do you know the complication of oxygen toxicity?	130	96.3	3	2.2	1.02
8.	Do you know the medical treatment of oxygen toxicity?	132	97.8	1	0.7	1.01
9.	Do you know the nursing intervention in case of oxygen toxicity occurrence?	133	98.5	0	0	1.00

Section No. 2

This section checked nurse's practices regarding safe oxygen administration therapy

Before oxygen administration practices

Table 7 shows that nurses practices regarding safe oxygen administration therapy. Verify physician prescription before administration 90.4% (n= 122) participants done, 8.1% (n= 11) not done. Wash

hands 79.3% (n= 107) done, 19.3% (n= 26) not done. Prepare needed equipment 97.0% (n= 131) done, 1.5% (n= 2) not done. Introduce yourself to the patient 92.6% (n= 125) done, 5.9% (n=8) not done. Identify the patient 98.5% (n= 133) done, there were no participant who were not done. Explain procedure to the patient 91.9% (n= 124) done, 6.7% (n= 9) not done. Disinfect hands 93.3% (n= 126) done, 5.2% (n= 7) not done. Wear disposable gloves 80.7% (n= 109) done, 17.8% (n= 24) not done. The overall mean of all questions are 1.08.

Table 7. Practices before oxygen administration therapy

Sr.no	Statements	Done		Not done		Mean
		F	%	F	%	
1.	Verify physician prescription before administration	122	90.4	11	8.1	1.08
2.	Wash hands	107	79.3	26	19.3	1.20
3.	Prepare needed equipment	131	97.0	2	1.5	1.02
4.	Introduce yourself to the patient	125	92.6	8	5.9	1.06
5.	Identify the patient	133	98.5	0	0	1.00
6.	Explain procedure to the patient	124	91.9	9	6.7	1.07
7.	Disinfect hands	126	93.3	7	5.2	1.05
8.	Wear disposable gloves	109	80.7	24	17.8	1.18

During oxygen administration practices

Table 8 shows that nurses practices during oxygen administration. Assess patient oxygen saturation 94.1% (n= 127) done, 4.4% (n= 6) not done. Assess patient respiratory status for normal and abnormal finding 94.8% (n= 128) done, 3.7% (n= 5) not done. Connect flow meter to the oxygen supply 98.5% (n= 133) done, there were no participant who were not done. Fill humidifier with suitable amount of distilled water 95.6% (n=129) done, 3.0% (n= 4) not done. Open oxygen supply before connecting oxygen device to the patient 98.5% (n= 133) done, there were no participant who were not done. Connect oxygen device to the oxygen setup with humidification 98.5% (n= 133) done, there were no participant who were not done. Adjust flow rate of oxygen according to prescribed rate 98.5% (n= 133) done, there were no participant who were not done. Connect oxygen therapy device to the patient appropriately 98.5% (n= 133) done, there were no participant who were not done. Connect tubing over and behind each ear with adjuster

comfortable to patient 97.0% (n= 131) done, 1.5% (n= 2) not done. Place tubing around the patients head with the adjuster at the back or base of the head 91.9% (n= 124) done, 5.2% (n= 7) not done. Place gauze pads at ear beneath the tubing, if necessary 92.6% (n= 125) done, 4.4% (n= 6) not done. Adjust the fit of the device tubing to make patient feel comfort 97.8% (n= 132) done, 7% (n= 1) not done. Reassess the patients respiratory status 98.5% (n= 133) done, there were no participant who were not done. The overall mean of all questions are 0.93.

Table 8. Practices during oxygen administration therapy

Sr.no	Statements	Done		Not done		Mean
		F	%	F	%	
1.	Assess patients oxygen saturation	127	94.1	6	4.4	1.05
2.	Assess patient respiratory status for normal and abnormal finding	128	94.8	5	3.7	1.04
3.	Connect flow meter to the oxygen supply	133	98.5	0	0	1.00
4.	Fill humidifier with suitable amount of distilled water	129	95.6	4	3.0	1.03
5.	Open oxygen supply before connecting oxygen device to the patient	133	98.5	0	0	1.00
6.	Connect oxygen device to the oxygen setup with humidification	133	98.5	0	0	1.00
7.	Adjust flow rate of oxygen according to prescribed rate	133	98.5	0	0	1.00
8.	Connect oxygen therapy device to the patient appropriately	133	98.5	0	0	1.00
9.	Connect tubing over and behind each ear with adjuster comfortable to patient	131	97.0	2	1.5	1.02
10.	Place tubing around the patients head with the adjuster at the back or base of the head	124	91.9	7	5.2	1.05
11.	Place gauze pads at ear beneath the tubing, if necessary	125	92.6	6	4.4	1.05
12.	Adjust the fit of the device, tubing to make patient feel comfort	132	97.8	1	7	1.01
13.	Reassess the patients respiratory status	133	98.5	0	0	1.00

After oxygen administration therapy

Table shows that nurses practices after oxygen administration therapy. Discard used equipment 95.6% (n= 129) done, 3.0% (n= 4) were not done. Remove

gloves 88.9% (n= 120) done, 9.6% (n= 13) were not done. The overall mean of all questions were 1.045.

Table 9. Practices after oxygen administration therapy

Sr.no	Statements	Done		Not done		Mean
		F	%	F	%	
1.	Discard used equipment	129	95.6	4	3.0	1.05
2.	Remove gloves	120	88.9	13	9.6	1.04

DISCUSSION

Data collected from the tertiary care hospital the study population was nurses of this hospital and the sample size was 133 nurses. Total 98.5% of female nurses who choose for the study represent the whole graduate and experienced nurses in Sheikh Zayed hospital Lahore. The age participation of the nurses were from 20-60 years. The participants nurses including graduated nurses, diploma holder nurses, nurses who have more than 1 year of experience. The study was conducted in different ICUs, emergency, and medical and surgical wards. The likert scale questionnaire used to conduct the nurses knowledge about the safe oxygen therapy. 97.8% participants know the aim of oxygen administration therapy. 100.0% participants know the indication of oxygen therapy. 100.0% know the method of assessing oxygen saturation in the blood. 95.6% participants were aware about the precaution during administration oxygen therapy. 94.8% participants know about the oxygen toxicity. 97.0% participants know about the sign and symptoms of oxygen toxicity. 96.3% participants know about the complications of oxygen toxicity. 97.8% participants know about the medical treatment of oxygen toxicity. 98.5% participants know the nursing intervention in case of oxygen toxicity occurrence. In this study the observational checklist were used to check nurses practices (before, during, and after) the safe oxygen administration therapy. Before oxygen administration 90.4% participants were verified physician prescription before oxygen administration. 79.3% participants were washed hand. 97.0% participants were prepared needed equipment before oxygen administration. 92.6% participants were introduced themselves to the patients. 98.5% were identified patient. 91.9% participants were explained procedure to the patient. 93.3% participants have disinfected hands. 80.7% participants wear disposable gloves. 94.1% assessed patient's oxygen saturation. 94.8% assessed patient respiratory status for normal and abnormal finding. 98.5% were connect flow meter to the oxygen supply. 95.6% were filled humidifier with suitable amount of distilled water. 98.5% were open oxygen supply before connecting oxygen device to the patient. 98.5% were connecting oxygen device to the oxygen setup with humidification. 98.5% were adjust flow rate of oxygen according to prescribed rate. 98.5% were

connected oxygen therapy device to the patient appropriately. 97.0% were connected tubing over and over behind each ear with adjuster comfortable to patient. 91.9% were placed tubing around the patients head with the adjuster at the back or base of the head. 92.6% were placed gauze pads at ear beneath the tubing, if necessary. 97.8% were adjusted the fit of the device, tubing to make patient feel comfort. 98.5% were reassessing the patients' respiratory status. 95.6% were discard used equipment. 88.9% were removed gloves. The overall result of this study shows that all participants know the safe oxygen administration therapy to patient.

CONCLUSION

The study finding shows that most of the nurses know about the safe oxygen administration therapy. In this study there is no any protocol that nurses could not followed for oxygen therapy. The experienced nurses and bachelor nurses have much knowledge about the safe oxygen administration therapy. This study concluded that, a majority of the studied sample had satisfactory level of knowledge and has a adequate level of practices.

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